

Ketu – Seven Stages of Liberation

43 Comments / English Blogs / By Deepanshu Giri

Today on Shanivaar, Shasti Tithi- when you feel bondage, Let me try to give you relief by talking about Moksh karaka- Ketu. The energy of Ketu is to liberate so the cycle of birth & death could be ended, As Ketu rules Scorpio along with Mars, which gives the option of coming back or ending the Journey by being liberated.

Liberation has stages, people who are on the path of liberation know that it doesn't happen in a day but over a period of time by crossing the obstacle, which is in front of you, Sometimes the obstacle is of the physical body (Mars), sometimes of name (Mercury), Fame (Sun), Family (Venus), Home (Moon) and even sometimes of Knowledge (Jupiter) or what we precise as Karma(Saturn).

Ketu when conjoined with a planet, teaches you to move forward like an Arrow rather than going in circles, following the same traditional path same as Ketu-this is from where the name has come from (Dhoom Ketu)- the star which breaks the pattern from the sky and travels to another galaxy as changing realms is the domain of Ketu.

Sun being the Soul significator keep all the planets revolving around Sun, but once in a while, some soul manages to liberate the Soul by exiting the Solar System. Ketu is the shooting star of the Sky, which has managed to break the patterns of life and death and exited the solar system- All planets revolve around Sun but once in a while some soul completes its journey and manage to travel to feet of Vishnu by breaking the bondage of Soul (Sun)

As saints practice this by leaving their house as they are doing is the one who leaves their birthplace, and home cross the barrier of the Moon, Then comes Sun -Ego, Saints do it by practising food discipline and begging for food, and Then comes the desire for family that is taken off by being single and not getting attached to anyone, During Sanyas the new name is given by Guru so the name from which you identify yourself is also gone, then Guru takes the ego of knowledge by showing student real knowledge and finally the Karma of not being attached to any karma native is doing.

Ketu with Venus harms the sperm count as with the help of new life is given, Ketu opposes that in a body- When conjoined with Sun native is asked to sacrifice his fame, sleep, and work for everyone else as being a leader is not an easy task, these are kingmakers, who help others grow When in conjunction with Moon, native is asked to sacrifice for the emotional body, food, home.

Ketu in conjunction with Mars is a lower category as in past life native, native was too attached to his physical body, ego and these are the people in past who were in front of the mirror appreciating themselves, So in this life, these natives are born with a combination where they can't be proud of health, This is one of the simple ways to understand it as Mars Ketu in each of different house will behave in a different manner.

Ketu in conjunction with Mercury, natives who are too proud of memory, name, relations, and siblings are given trouble in these areas to be humble and serve these people to get free from bondage, Ketu in conjunction with Jupiter are the ones who were perfect in philanthropy, Social law but too involved in it and forget that this is the only path for liberation and after a certain time you need to leave everything and move on to the higher goal.

Saturn with Ketu is a karma of higher order, which is given to people who have reached the peak of their career in a past life and were unable to move on, too attached to the karma by taking responsibility for everyone and in this life, Ketu teaches them to be idle for a long time so they can learn, the world does not revolve on their shoulders, Even when they don't go to the office, work will be done, this is the final barrier.

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PRIYESH

24 JUNE 2023 AT 11:57

Excellent sir..plz give remedy for venus ketu in 4th house libra sign..

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SHRABANI SIL

24 JUNE 2023 AT 12:17

Outstanding Sir. I bow to your wisdom with all my heart. I wish I could meet you, touch your feet and have you as my Guru and learn astrology from you. And this is my Heart's Desire.

Edit

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PARTHASARTTHI DAAS

24 JUNE 2023 AT 13:01